

Preparation, Infrared Absorption and X-ray Powder Diffraction Patterns of Calcium Cobalt(II) Hydroxyapatites and Their Solid Solutions

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Manuscript received 13 January 1981, revised 23 March 1983, accepted 30 March 1983

Homogeneous solid solutions of cobalt and calcium hydroxyapatite have been prepared over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation in aqueous media. Frequencies and assignments for the infrared absorption and the lattice constants of the solid solutions have been measured and found to vary linearly with composition between those of the pure and the members.

CALCIUM hydroxyapatite (CaHA), $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, the principal inorganic constituent of human bones and teeth¹ belongs to the isomorphous series of compounds, the apatites. Calcium hydroxyapatite (CaHA) also exists in nature as the mineral hydroxyapatite which is similar, if not identical, to that of the bone mineral and can be prepared from aqueous media^{2,3}. The ionic radii⁴ of calcium (0.99 Å) and cobalt(II) (0.74 Å) are fairly close and hence solid solutions may be formed between isomorphous substances containing these ions. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions⁵. The $\text{Ca}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{2+}$ replacement reaction in CaHA is of extreme biological significance since its effect on calcified tissue is interesting. The reaction forms the basis of incorporation of Co^{2+} into human skeletal system. The exchange process results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of CaHA and cobalt hydroxyapatite (CoHA), $\text{Co}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, and when made to proceed till completion leads to the formation of pure CoHA according to the equation :

Solid solutions of calcium and cobalt hydroxyapatites were prepared earlier⁶ by fixing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium hydroxyapatite and cobalt hydroxyapatite at about 1300°. However, these samples prepared by solid state reaction were found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. An attempt has been made in the present study to develop a new method of preparation of homogeneous solid solutions over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation⁷⁻⁹.

Experimental

Materials : Chemicals used for the preparation of these samples were of either BDH A.R. or E. Merck, E.P. grade. Water used for the prepara-

tion and washing was boiled to remove CO_2 and used immediately.

Preparations : Solutions of stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (solution A) and solutions containing calcium(II) and cobalt(II) ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (solution B) were prepared separately in CO_2 free double distilled water. The pH of the solutions was maintained above 11 by the addition of ethylene diamine. A part of the solution B was then taken in a flask (2l) fitted with two separating funnels and a delivery tube. Solution A and solution B were taken in the separating funnels and added dropwise to the flask simultaneously. Precipitation was also carried out in CO_2 free atmosphere to prevent the formation of carbonato-apatites.

The precipitate and mother liquor were aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate. Maintenance of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate, since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium deficient apatites¹⁰. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with double distilled water to free it from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 100° for a few hr were analysed complexometrically¹¹ and their molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene¹² as a solvent.

Infrared absorption techniques : Samples used for infrared studies were washed and air dried. All the bands were recorded on a Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrophotometer model 577 in KBr medium. A few milligrams of the sample was ground with two drops of nujol in an agate mortar. About 50 mg of a fine polyethylene powder (VESTOLENA 6016 Chem. Werke Huels, Germany) was added. The resulting paste was melted rapidly at about 140° and pressed between glass plates to a slightly wedge-shaped film of average thickness 0.1 mm.

X-ray diffraction techniques: Samples dried at 110° for a few hr were used for X-ray diffraction studies. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with Siemens Powder diffractometer with NaCl(Tl) counter employing CuK_α (Nickel filtered) radiation with a scanning speed of 1 degree (2 θ) per min (using tube voltage of 30 kV and 24 mA, respectively).

Lattice constant measurements: Both CaHA and CoHA are hexagonal with two lattice constants a₀ and c₀. These were determined^{13,14} for all the samples by measuring the diffraction angle, 2 θ, of the three planes, (312), (213) and (321). Each sample was thoroughly mixed with 25% NaCl (recrystallized from HCl) which served as a standard so that the observed values of sin θ for the solid solution lines could be corrected directly for absorption and instrumental errors. The lattice constant of NaCl at 26° was taken to be 5.6403 Å¹⁵. A least squares calculation on the corrected values of sin θ for the three reflections then gave the two parameters, a₀ and c₀ for each sample. The average probable error in unit cell parameters is less than ± 0.05 Å.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples are given in Table 1. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g atoms of calcium and/or cobalt, the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated from the results of columns 2-4 and

those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of the end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by the X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal-bipyramidal class -6/m- (space group P_{6₃/m})^{16,17}. Lattice parameters showed unit cell contraction consequent upon the substitution of smaller ion. Such contraction with the proportion of CoHA was evident from the excellent regularity with which the unit cell volume of the samples, calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant, decreased with the proportion of CoHA. This, of course, is the real evidence for solid solution in this series and clearly shows that these preparations are not mixtures of two components.

The ideal symmetry of phosphate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of T_d point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only absorption bands corresponding to ν₄ (570 cm⁻¹) and ν₃ (1075 cm⁻¹) of PO₄³⁻ were clearly observed. The shift of the ν₃ and ν₄ of PO₄³⁻ vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. G. Ferraris, University of Torino (Italy) for X-ray data, Dr. M. M. Dhar, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for ir spectra,

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COBALT HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample No.	Wt %			Molecular formulae	Mol. vol	g. atom ratio Ca+Co P	Lattice parameter (Å)		Unit cell vol. √ ³ / ₂ a ² c	Frequency (cm ⁻¹) PO ₄ ³⁻ PO ₄ ³⁻	
	Ca	Co	P				a	c		ν ₄	ν ₃
1	39.88	—	18.51	Ca ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	338.32	1.665	9.37	6.86	523.12	570	1075
2	36.16	4.62	18.24	Ca _{9.9} Co _{0.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	336.25	1.655					
3	31.20	10.76	17.87	Ca _{8.1} Co _{1.9} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	330.96	1.662	9.28	6.80	507.15	568	1072
4	27.50	15.34	17.60	Ca _{7.95} Co _{2.75} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	333.81	1.664					
5	21.45	22.58	17.17	Ca _{5.95} Co _{4.15} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	332.96	1.666	9.16	6.75	490.48	565	1070
6	18.83	26.07	16.97	Ca _{5.15} Co _{4.85} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	339.75	1.660					
7	14.34	31.63	16.64	Ca ₄ Co ₆ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	240.72	1.665	9.06	6.72	477.70	560	1065
8	11.13	35.60	16.40	Ca _{3.15} Co _{6.85} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	348.25	1.665					
9	7.48	40.13	16.14	Ca _{2.15} Co _{7.85} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	342.76	1.665	9.02	6.66	469.26	556	1062
10	4.28	44.08	15.90	Ca _{1.75} Co _{8.75} (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	350.64	1.664					
11	—	49.38	15.59	Co ₁₀ (PO ₄) ₆ (OH) ₂	340.18	1.665	8.96	6.58	457.48	555	1060

included in column 5 of Table 1. The g atom ratio $\left(\frac{Ca+Co}{P}\right)$ in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of columns 2-4 and given in column 7. The fact that the observed value of molar g atom ratios of $\frac{Ca}{P}$, $\frac{Co}{P}$ for the end members and of $\frac{Ca+Co}{P}$ for the intermediates were found to be equal to 1.664 (theoretical 1.67) is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solutions¹². This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and

and the University Grants Commission for financial support.

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